

Oxo-Molybdenum (V) Complexes of 8-Hydroxyquinoline and Substituted 8-Hydroxyquinolines. Part IV

R. L. Dutta* and B. Chatterjee

A number of oxo-molybdenum (V) complexes of 8-hydroxyquinoline, 5, 7-dibromo 8-hydroxyquinoline and 5, 7-dichloro 8-hydroxyquinoline have been synthesized and characterised. These are of the types:

(where oxin H = 8-hydroxyquinoline, χ = pyridine, β -picoline or γ -picoline and O-phen = O-phenanthroline).

These complexes are all highly coloured, crystalline and quite stable to air. Most of these complexes are diamagnetic or show poor paramagnetic values. The reflectance spectra are characteristic of oxo-molybdenum (V) complexes.

We have reported in Parts I and II¹ of this series a large number of oxo-molybdenum (V) complexes of quinoline and pyridine carboxylic acid ligands. A few of the complexes, namely, $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_4\text{Q}_2(\text{O-phen})]$ and $[\text{MoO}_2\text{Q.X}]$ (where QH = quinaldinic acid; O-phen = O-Phenanthroline and X = pyridine or picolines) were unique. Quite logically we desired to extend these studies to other potential inner metallic ligands and favourable results were obtained with 8-hydroxyquinoline and its substituted derivatives.

A few complexes of oxo-molybdenum (V) with 8-hydroxyquinoline have already been reported in the literature. These are: (1) $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{oxine})_2]^2$, (2) $[\text{MoO}(\text{OH})(\text{oxine})_2]^2$, (3) $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3(\text{oxine})_4]$, $4\text{H}_2\text{O}^3$, (4) $\text{H}_2[\text{Mo}_4\text{O}_{11}(\text{oxine})_7]$ $11\text{H}_2\text{O}^3$, and (5) in solution (1:1) complex with HQSA⁴ (where Oxine H = 8-hydroxyquinoline, HQSA = 8-hydroxyquinoline-5, sulphonic acid). We report here several new complexes of oxo-molybdenum (V) with oxine and its 5,7-dichloro- and 5,7-dibromo derivatives.

I. *μ -O-Phenanthroline-dioxo-tetrachloro-bis (oxinato)—dimolybdenum (V)*: This complex is obtained as a heavy crystalline maroon coloured product when a hot ethanolic solution of oxine (1 mole) and ammonium oxo-pentachloro molybdate (1 mole) is treated with O-phenanthroline (0.5 mole). The complex is insoluble in all common organic solvents and is very stable to air. The reactions probably are:

The complex is diamagnetic indicating very effective spin-spin interaction in the system. The insolubility of the complex did not permit any conductance measurement.

* Present address—Department of Chemistry, Ohio State University (U.S.A.).

1. R. L. Dutta and B. Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 759; 1967, **44**, 684.

That the complex is not merely a mixture of $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{oxine})_2]^2$ and $[\text{MoOCl}_3(\text{O-phen})]^{4a}$ is proven through an examination of the properties of these two complexes. Both have reported as green coloured material and have been found to be paramagnetic [$\text{MoOCl}(\text{oxine})_2$, 1.36 B.M. and $\text{MoOCl}_3(\text{O-phen})$, 1.71 B.M.]. We have also isolated the complex $\text{MoOCl}(\text{oxine})_2$ by a modified procedure and have found a para magnetism of 1.22 B.M.

The diffuse reflectance spectra of complex provide bands at $24,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $19,200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and at around $14,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. These bands are characteristic of oxo-molybdenum (V) complexes^{5a-c} and represent the transitions $dxy \rightarrow dz^2$, $dxy \rightarrow dx^2-y^2$ and $dxy \rightarrow dxz$, dyz respectively. Our earlier comments on assuming the ground state as singlet and the d-d transitions spreading over two metal centres should also hold good here.

Our attempts to determine the oxidation state of molybdenum in this complex or in the others in this series did not quite materialise. However, the position of the visible spectral bands leave little doubt as to the quinquevalency of molybdenum in these complexes. Prolonged shaking of the complex with 12M hydrochloric acid at ordinary temperature furnished a light yellow-green colour, characteristic of oxo-molybdenum (V) in the above acid⁶.

II. *Bis (Pyridine/picoline) tetraoxo-bis (oxinato)-dimolybdenum (V)*: These complexes are obtained as bright orange-red crystals by the addition of pyridine, β -picoline or γ -picoline to a refluxing solution of oxine (1 mole) and oxo molybdenum (V) chloride (1 mole). On cooling or on concentrating crystals appear. These are also all insoluble in common organic solvents and further these are all diamagnetic (Table I). These properties are indicative of a largely dimeric structure.

The reflectance spectra of the complex of this type $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{DBO})_2(\text{py})_2]$ (where DBO = 5.7-dibromo 8-hydroxyquinoline) exhibits two bands around $25,300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $13,600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, the middle bands apparently being unresolved under the strong energy band (Table II). This often happens with oxo-molybdenum (V) complexes. The complexes, however, provide the characteristic green colour of MoOCl_3 when treated with 12M hydrochloric acid. The complexes reveal a strong molybdenyl band around 950 cm^{-1} .

2. P. Mitchell and R. Williams, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 4570.
3. A. Bseev and Chan-Fan, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1960, 55, 8151.
4. J. Spence and E. Peterson, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 277.
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6. M. Larson and F. Moore, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 2, 881.

TABLE I
Magnetic Measurements
Temp. = 30°

Compounds	Colour	Dia. corr. $\times 10^{-6}$	$M_{corr} \times 10^{-6}$	μ eff* (B.M.)
[Mo ₂ O ₂ Cl ₄ (oxine) (O-phen)]	Maroon	—	—	Diamag.
[MoOCl (oxine) ₂]	Dark-green	206.3	613.4	1.22**
[MoOCl (DBO) ₂]	Dark-green	154.5	372.5	1.02
[Mo ₂ O ₄ (oxine) ₂ (py) ₂]	Orange-red	—	—	Diamag.
[Mo ₂ O ₄ (oxine) ₂ (β -picoline) ₂]	Red	—	—	Diamag.
[Mo ₂ O ₄ (oxine) ₂ (γ -picoline) ₂]	Red	—	—	Diamag.
[Mo ₂ O ₄ (DBO) ₂ (Py) ₂]	Orange-brown	192.5	200.6	0.70
[Mo ₂ O ₄ (DBO) ₂ (β -picoline) ₂]	Orange-brown	—	—	Diamag.
[Mo ₂ O ₄ (DBO) ₂ (γ -picoline) ₂]	Orange	—	—	Diamag.
[Mo ₂ O ₄ (DCO) ₂ (py) ₂]	Red	—	—	Diamag.
[MoO ₂ (DCO) ₂]	Golden yellow	—	—	Diamag.

* Calculated from $\chi_{M_{corr}}$ using Curie equation, μ eff. = 2.84 ($\lambda_{M_{corr}}XT$)[†]

** Other reported value is 1.36 (Ref. 2) (DCO = 5,7-dibromo oxine; DCC = 5,7-dichloro oxine and py = pyridine).

TABLE II
Reflectance spectra of the complexes

Complex	λ_{max} ($m\mu$)	Wave number (cm^{-1})	Probable assignment
[Mo ₂ O ₄ (DBO) ₂ (py) ₂]	394	25,300	dxy → dz ²
	734	13,600	dxy → dxz, dyz
[Mo ₂ O ₂ Cl ₄ (oxine)(O-phen)]	415	24,060	dxy → dz ²
	520	19,230	dxy → dx ² - y ²
	710-722	14,084-13,850	dxy → dxz, dyz

III. *Oxo-Chloro-bis(oxinato)-molybdenum (V)*: A simple and quicker method, compared to that of Mitchell and Williams², of obtaining this species by refluxing oxo-molybdenum (V) chloride (1 mole) and oxine (2.5 mole) in anhydrous ethanol has been developed. This forms dark green crystals and provides a magnetic moment of about 1.22 B.M., compared to 1.36 B.M. reported earlier². The dibromo derivative also shows a similar reaction; surprisingly the 5,7-dichlorooxine apparently provides a shining golden yellow product, which is diamagnetic and whose chloroform spectra shows no ligand field bands—instead only a charge transfer band (λ_{max} . 340 $m\mu$, $\epsilon = 645$) characteristic of Mo(VI).

EXPERIMENTAL

5,7-dibromooxine and 5,7-dichlorooxine were prepared by following standard procedures and were recrystallised from alcohol⁷. Ammonium oxo-pentachloro molybdate (V)

7. Welcher, "Organic Analytical Reagents", D. Van Nostrand Co. Inc., New Jersey, 1948., Vol. I, pp. 323, 329.

(emerald green) was also synthesised by following standard procedure^{7a}. All refluxing was done on a sand bath and no special precaution was taken to exclude air and moisture.

1. *μ-O-phenanthroline-dioxo-tetrachloro-bis (oxinato)-dimolybdenum (V) (Maroon)*: Oxine (0.3 g), dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (5.0 ml), was mixed with a filtered solution of ammonium oxo-pentachloro molybdate (V) (0.65 g) dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (20.0 ml). Immediately, a dark-red solution formed. This was then refluxed for 15 minutes and *o*-phenanthroline (0.18 g), dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (10.0 ml.) was added to this solution. Immediately, a heavy crystalline maroon compound settled. This was refluxed for 10 minutes, cooled, filtered, washed several times with anhydrous ethanol and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: Mo, 23.9%; N, 7.0%, Cl, 17.0%. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_4(\text{oxine})_2(\text{O-phen})]$ requires Mo, 23.0%, N, 6.7%; Cl, 17.2%.

2. *Oxo-Chloro-bis(oxinato)-molybdenum (V) (Dark green)*: Oxine (0.6 g), dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (10.0 ml.) was added to a filtered solution of ammonium oxo-penta chloro-molybdate (V) (0.65 g.), dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (20.0 ml.). Immediately, a maroon colour developed which when refluxed for 15 minutes, a dark green precipitate settled. This was further refluxed for 10 minutes, cooled, filtered, washed several times with anhydrous ethanol and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: Mo, 23.0%; N, 6.6%; Cl, 9.0%. $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{oxine})_2]$ requires: Mo, 22.08%; N, 6.4%; Cl, 8.1%.

3. *Oxo-Chloro-bis(bromo oxinato)-molybdenum (V) (Dark green)* was obtained as above using 5,7-dibromooxine (0.95 g.) in place of oxine. The solvent used for bromo oxine was anhydrous chloroform, alcohol mixture. Found: Mo, 13.3%; N, 3.7%; Cl, 4.5%. $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{DBO})_2]$ requires: Mo, 12.77%; N, 3.7%; Cl, 4.7%.

4. *Bis (Pyridine)-tetraoxo-bis (oxinato)-dimolybdenum (V) (Orange red)*: Ammonium oxo pentachloro molybdate (V) (0.65 g), dissolved in rectified spirit (15.0 ml.), was filtered and this solution was added to oxine (0.3 g) solution in rectified spirit (10.0 ml.). Immediately, a deep red solution was formed. This was refluxed for 10 minutes, when clear red solution was obtained. To this clear red solution pyridine (3.0 ml.) was added and the solution refluxed further for 10 minutes. On cooling, orange-red crystals formed. These were filtered, washed several times with rectified spirit and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: Mo, 28.0%; N, 8.2%. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{oxine})_2(\text{py})_2]$ requires Mo, 27.3%; N, 7.98%.

The substance liberates pyridine on heating with sodium hydroxide.

5. *Bis (β-picoline)-tetraoxo-bis (oxinato)-dimolybdenum (V) (Red)* was obtained as above using β-picoline (3.0 ml.) in place of pyridine. But on cooling no crystals separated. Some excess solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure when red crystals were obtained. Found: Mo, 26.0%; N, 7.6%. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{oxine})_2(\beta\text{-picoline})_2]$ requires: Mo, 26.2%; N, 7.6%.

6. *Bis (γ-picoline)-tetraoxo-bis (oxinato)-dimolybdenum (V) (Red)* was obtained as above using γ-picoline (3.0 ml.) in place of β-picoline. Found: Mo, 26.17%; N, 7.3%. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{oxine})_2(\gamma\text{-picoline})_2]$ requires Mo, 26.22%; N, 7.6%.

7. *Bis (Pyridine)-tetraoxo-bis (dibromo oxinato)-dimolybdenum (V) (Orange-brown)*: Dibromo oxine (0.62 g.) and pyridine (3.0 ml.) was refluxed for 10 minutes when most of the

7a. W. Palmer "Experimental Inorganic Chemistry", Cambridge University Press, 1954, p. 406.

reagent was dissolved. It was then filtered. Ammonium oxo-pentachloro molybdate (V) (0.65 g), dissolved in rectified spirit (15.0 ml.) was filtered from NH_4Cl and the solution added to the reagent solution. Immediately, a light orange precipitate settled but dissolved quickly on refluxing. This was then filtered and on cooling orange-brown crystals formed. These were filtered, washed several times with rectified spirit and dried over CaCl_2 . Found : Mo, 18.35%; N, 5.6%; Br, 30.7%. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{DBO})_2(\text{py})_2]$ requires : Mo, 18.8%; N, 5.5%; Br, 31.4%.

8. *Bis-(β -picoline)-tetraoxo-bis (dibromo oxinato)-dimolybdenum (V) (Orange-brown)* was obtained as above using β -picoline (2.5–3.0 ml.) in place of pyridine. Found : Mo, 18.7%; N, 5.6%; Br, 30.9%. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{DBO})_2(\beta\text{-picoline})_2]$ requires Mo, 18.3%; N, 5.3%; Br, 30.6%.

9. *Bis-(γ -picoline)-tetraoxo-bis(dibromo oxinato) dimolybdenum (V) (Orange)* was obtained as above using γ -picoline (3.0 ml.) in place of β -picoline. Found : Mo, 18.6%; N, 5.3%; Br, 31.4%. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{DBO})_2(\gamma\text{-picoline})_2]$ requires : Mo, 18.3%; N, 5.3%; Br, 30.6%.

10. *Bis(Pyridine)-tetraoxo-bis (dichloro-oxinato)-dimolybdenum (V) (Red)* was obtained as above using dichloro oxine (.44 g) and pyridine (3.0 ml.) respectively. Found : Mo, 22.6%; N, 6.1%; Cl, 17.8%. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4(\text{DCO})_2(\text{py})_2]$ requires : Mo, 22.8%; N, 6.6%; Cl, 16.9%.

11. *Bis (dichloro oxinato)-dioxo-molybdenum (VI) (Golden yellow)* : The reagent (1.30 g), dissolved in minimum volume of anhydrous ethanol-chloroform mixture by refluxing, was mixed with a filtered ethanolic solution of ammonium oxo-pentachloromolybdate (0.65 g). Immediately, a brown solution formed which quickly changed to orange-yellow. This solution was refluxed for 30 minutes when golden yellow crystals separated. These were cooled, filtered, washed with anhydrous ethanol and finally dried over CaCl_2 . Found : Mo, 16.98%; N, 4.80%; Cl, 25.2%. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{DCO})_2]$ requires : Mo, 17.3%; N, 5.0%; Cl, 25.6%.

The sample gave no test for chloride ion.

Analytical Methods : Molybdenum content was determined either (a) by decomposing the complex with equal volumes of conc. H_2SO_4 and HNO_3 and then after adjusting the pH precipitating molybdenum with oxine, and finally weighing as $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{oxine})_2]$ or by (b) decomposing the complex with alkali-hydrogen peroxide and then precipitating and weighing as $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{oxine})_2]$.

In the latter procedure, a known weight of complex was taken in an iodine flask and decomposed by refluxing in a steam bath for one hour with a mixture of strong NaOH and a few ml of H_2O_2 . The organic residue was then removed completely by extraction with chloroform^{5b}. After removal of the organic residue, estimation of Mo as $\text{MoO}_2(\text{oxine})_2$ was done as usual.

Estimation of ring-substituted halogens (chlorine and bromine) were made by decomposing the complex with alkali-hydrogen peroxide, molybdenum was then removed as oxinate and halides precipitated as Ag X ($\text{X} = \text{Cl/Br}$). This was filtered, dissolved in ammonia and reprecipitated with dil. HNO_3 and finally weighed as AgX . In the case of halogens attached to molybdenum, the complexes were decomposed with HNO_3 and silver halides estimated by double precipitation.

Nitrogen was estimated by semi micro combustion technique.

Magnetic Measurements : The magnetic susceptibility was determined by the Gouy method using a semi micro Mettler Balance for measuring the difference in weight with a field strength of 8.57×10^3 gauss. Diamagnetic corrections were taken from Selwood⁸. Recrystallised copper sulphate pentahydrate was used as a calibrant.

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Inorganic Chemistry Laboratory,
The University of Burdwan,
Burdwan, West Bengal.

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8. P. Selwood, "Magnetochemistry", Interscience, 1958, p. 91.